

Kinetics of Cobalt(III) Oxidations: Part I : Oxidation of Water

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The kinetics of oxidation of water by cobalt(III) in sulphuric acid medium at its 2, 2.5 and 3.5 M and ionic strength 3.75 M using the temperature range 30°, 35° and 40° have been studied. The order of the reaction has been found to be varying between one and two with respect to cobalt(III) concentrations. The rate of the reaction has been found to be inversely proportional to the first power of hydrogen ion concentration. $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$, $\text{CoOH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5^{2+}$, and $(\text{Co}-\text{O}-\text{CoOH})^{3+}$ has been shown to be the reactive species and a free radical mechanism consistent with the observed experimental facts proposed. Effect of sulphate and bisulphate ions on the reaction rate has also been studied.

TRIVALENT cobalt is very reactive and its reaction with water follows the overall course given by Noyes and Deahl².

Several workers²⁻⁶ have studied the kinetics of the reaction of cobalt(III) with water in sulphuric acid medium and reported variable order both for cobalt(III) and hydrogen ion. Therefore, the present work has been undertaken to reinvestigate the kinetics and mechanism of this reaction.

Experimental

Reagents : Sodium cobaltic carbonate complex was prepared and estimated by the method of Laitinen and Burdett⁷ and cobalt(III), *in situ*, was generated from the interaction of this complex and sulphuric acid in the reaction medium. All chemicals were of Analar grade. Ionisation of sulphuric acid in presence of sodium bisulphate in the reaction medium to calculate the ionic strength of the reaction medium was assumed to be as given by Bawn and White⁸.

Kinetic measurement : Solution containing appropriate concentration of substrate, mineral acid, and sodium bisulphate were allowed to reach a steady temperature in 6×1 in. pyrex tube immersed in thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) and then a specific volume of sodium cobaltic carbonate, also at the thermostat temperature, was introduced into the pyrex tube to react with water. Volume of the contents of the tube was always kept at 100 ml. The course of the reaction was followed by estimating the amount of unreacted cobalt(III)⁷.

It is found that the plot of log K against inverse of temperature gives a straight line indicating the validity of Arrhenius equation for the reaction over this temperature range.

Discussion

It is clearly seen from Table 1 that the rate of the reaction falls off with the progress of time and consequently the order of the reaction lies between one and

two. From Table 2 it could be concluded that as concentration of cobalt(III) increases, there is a gradual fall in the rate constants.

TABLE 1—A TYPICAL KINETIC RUN

Cobalt(III) = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2M$;
Ionic strength = 3.75M ; Temperature = 30°.

Time in min.	10	20	30	40	50	60
$10^4 K(\text{min}^{-1})$	50.12	49.15	48.10	47.95	46.32	45.92

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF THE RATE WITH THE CONCENTRATION OF COBALT(III)

$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.5M$; Ionic strength = 3.75M ; Temperature = 30°.

Concentration of cobalt(III)M	1×10^{-3}	2×10^{-3}	3×10^{-3}
$10^4 K(\text{min}^{-1})$ (ave.)	42.75	37.50	31.90

Plot of average first order rate constants against the reciprocal of hydrogen ion concentration (Table 3) was almost linear with intercept on the ordinate, the latter emphasizing the acid independent reaction. The acid dependent reaction can be explained by the following equilibrium^{3,4,8}, while acid independent reaction

may be due to either CoSO_4^+ or $\text{Co(III) aq. species}$. Sulphate as well as bisulphate ion effects on the reaction rate exclude the possibility of CoSO_4^+ being the active species (Table 5). Therefore $\text{CoOH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5^{2+}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ are the active species along with $(\text{Co}-\text{O}-\text{CoOH})^{3+}$, which has been suggested by several workers^{3,4,5,9} the addition of cobalt(II) of the reaction mixture was found to lower the reaction rate very little (Table 4).

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF THE RATE WITH HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION.

Cobalt(III) = $1 \times 10^{-8} M$; Ionic strength = $3.75 M$; Temperature = 30° .

Concentration of sulphuric acid (M)	2	2.5	3
$10^4 K(\text{min}^{-1})$	47.25	40.22	35.03

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF COBALT(II) ON THE REACTION RATE.

Cobalt(III) = $1 \times 10^{-8} M$; Ionic strength = $3.75 M$; $H_2SO_4 = 2.5 M$; Temperature = 30° .

Cobalt(II) $\times 10^8 M$	0	0.5	1.5	2
$10^4 K(\text{min}^{-1})$	42.15	41.92	41.35	41.21

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF BISULPHATE ION ON THE REACTION RATE.

Cobalt(III) = $1 \times 10^{-8} M$; $H_2SO_4 = 2 M$; Ionic strength = $3.75 M$; Temperature = 35° .

$(H_2SO_4 + NaHSO_4), M$	2	2.52	3.12	3.69
$10^4 K(\text{min}^{-1})$	114.55	117.32	117.73	117.52

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE REACTION RATE.

Cobalt(III) = $1 \times 10^{-8} M$; Ionic strength = $3.75 M$; $H_2SO_4 = 2 M$.

Temperature $0^\circ C$	30	35	40	E
$10^4 K(\text{min}^{-1})$	48.16	144.55	243.92	k.cal/mole 50.20

From the above discussion, the reaction mechanism consistent with the present investigation is as under :

and the rate equation will be

$$\begin{aligned}
 -d(\text{Co}^{3+})/dt &= K_1(\text{Co}^{3+}) + K_2(\text{CoOH}^{2+}) + K_3(\text{Co-O-CoOH}^{3+}) \\
 \text{or } -d(\text{Co}^{3+})/dt &= K_1(\text{Co}^{3+}) + K_2 K(\text{Co}^{3+})/(\text{H}^+) + K_3 K''(\text{Co-O-Co}^{4+})/(\text{H}^+) \\
 \text{or } -d(\text{Co}^{3+})/dt &= K_1(\text{Co}^{3+}) + K_2 K(\text{Co}^{3+})/(\text{H}^+) + K_3 K'' K'(\text{Co}^{3+})^2/(\text{H}^+) \\
 \text{or } -d(\text{Co}^{3+})/dt &= K_1(\text{Co}^{3+}) + K'_2(\text{Co}^{3+})/(\text{H}^+) + K'_3(\text{Co}^{2+})^2/(\text{H}^+)
 \end{aligned}$$

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